

Livelihood Assessment of Farmer Households in in Thai Nguyen Province, Vietnam

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Abstract:

Farm households play an important role in socio-economic development in rural areas in particular and Thai Nguyen province in general. Sustainable livelihood development for farmers is an urgent goal of the province in the current period. The article outlines the livelihoods of farmers and then points out some policy solutions to support household livelihoods in the period 2025-2030.

Keywords: Farming households, livelihoods, sustainable livelihoods, Thai Nguyen

1. Introduction

In recent years, Thai Nguyen province has been severely affected by the Covid-19 pandemic, affecting the lives of all people in Thai Nguyen province, including farmers. Despite the rise of the unemployment rate and the decrease in income, with the efforts of the people and the entire provincial government, people's life was maintained stably and the situation of the security and social order, and safety was ensured. In 2020, the per capita income will reach 4.39 million VND/person/month, an increase of 0.37 million VND/person/month compared to 2019. In which, the urban area will reach 6.02 million VND/person /month, and rural areas get 3.54 million VND/person/month. Although less economically damaged than urban areas, rural areas are also more or less affected, especially farmers.

2. Overview of farmer households' livelihoods in Thai Nguyen province.

2.1. Resource characteristics of farm households in Thai Nguyen province.

2.1.1. Human Resources

Human resources (quantity and quality) of farmer households are shown in the following table:

Table 1: Number of farming households

Year	Number of households in the rural area (household)	Number of farmer households (household)	Percentage of farm households/total number of households in the rural area (%)
2011	223.755	172.488	77,1
2016	226.105	150.863	66,8
2020	248.998	121.727	48,9

Source: Thai Nguyen Provincial Statistics Office 2021 (1)

Table 1 shows different trends in the number of households. While rural households tend to increase from 223,755 households (2011) to 248,998 households (2020), the number of farm households tends to decrease to 50,761

households in the period 2011-2020. According to the author's calculation, the percentage of farming households in rural areas accounted for 77.1% in 2011; 66.8% in 2016, and reduced to less than 50% in 2020. This trend is consistent with the law, however, if the size of the farmer household does not increase while the average age of the household is aging, Thai Nguyen province is losing go team of professional farmers.

Although the number of farm households accounts for a large proportion in rural areas, the number of untrained workers is still high.

Source: Thai Nguyen Provincial Statistics Office, 2012, 2017, 2021.

Looking at chart 2, we see that the proportion of untrained agricultural, forestry, and fishery workers account for a large proportion. The number of untrained workers in 2011 was 334,476 people, in 2016 and 2020 it decreased by 280,180 people and 246,543 people, respectively. The proportion of trained workers tends to increase but is still not high. This affects the livelihood choices of workers as well as farmers in rural areas of Thai Nguyen province.

2.2.1.2. Land resources.

The land is an important resource and means of production for farmers in Thai Nguyen province. The agricultural land (including agricultural land, forestry land, aquaculture land, and other agricultural lands) has changed in a new direction: land for rice and annual crops decreased, land planting perennial crops, forestry land, and aquaculture land increased.

The annual cropland area decreased from 64,975.8ha in 2010 to 57,143ha, while aquaculture and forestry land increased by 14.4% and 3.7% respectively compared to 2010. Repurposed such agricultural land to produce higher livelihood outcomes. Besides, in 2010, the number of households owning a land size of less than 0.5ha accounted for 86.2%, this is a large number that hinders the process of industrialization and modernization in the agricultural sector. . Following the support policies of the State and Thai Nguyen province, the accumulation of land to form a large sample field has

gradually been formed but the results are not high, the number of farmer households owning from 5ha of land agriculture or more accounted for 0.01%.

2.1.3. Material resources.

*** House**

In recent years, the implementation of livelihood support policies has shown a significant change in the quality of life of farm households in Thai Nguyen province. In 2008, the percentage of households with semi-permanent houses was the highest at 58.26%, followed by the percentage of households with permanent houses (26.09%) and the lowest percentage of households with simple houses (15.66%). However, by 2020, the proportion of households living in permanent houses will increase to 96.4% and the proportion of households living in simple houses will decrease to 0.4%.

Source: Thai Nguyen Provincial Party Committee, 2021 (2)

*** Device connection information.**

Televisions, phones, and computers are three devices that help farmers access necessary information.

Source: Thai Nguyen Provincial Party Committee, 2021.

The percentage of farm households owning color televisions, phones, and computers increased rapidly in the period 2008-2020. In 2008, the percentage of households owning color televisions, telephones, and computers was 58.63%, 6.89%, and 0.96% respectively, by 2020 this rate will be 92.75%, 95.38% and 20.5%. This increase in number not only reflects the remarkable improvement in the living standards of farmers in Thai Nguyen province but also helps farmers get useful information about the weather, epidemics, and product consumption markets. products... create appropriate livelihood strategies and reduce livelihood risks. However, the percentage of households with computers is still relatively low and the use of information technology is not proficient as a barrier for farmers to expand production and business.

2.2.2. Main livelihood activities of farmers in Thai Nguyen province.

The main livelihood activities of rural households in Thai Nguyen province are agricultural livelihoods and non-agricultural livelihoods.

Agricultural livelihood activities include farming, animal husbandry, aquaculture, and forestry.

In 2016, the number of households growing annual crops accounted for the largest number, followed by livestock, perennial crops, forestry land use, and aquaculture (197,703 households, 176,487 households, 130,555 households, 71,729 households, and 40,789 households). households), by 2020, although there is a slight variation within the household's livelihood strategies, however, households growing annual crops account for the largest proportion (226,409 households), while households cultivating Fishery accounted for the lowest proportion with 25,001 households.

Livelihood farming activities:

With the advantage of land, farmer households in Thai Nguyen province mainly grow rice and tea. With the support of the State government and Thai Nguyen provincial government, the farming household has shifted to planting trees. planting produces better livelihood results.

For the rice: in the period 2010-2020, the area under rice cultivation tends to decrease from 48,128.32 ha to 42,897 ha due to the conversion of inefficient one-season rice land to other crops of high economic value. and combine rice farming and aquaculture. In addition, implementing the One Commune, One Product Program to promote sustainable livelihoods, Thai Nguyen province focuses on cultivating specialty and organic rice varieties that are advantageous in each commune with about 2,720 hectares per year. 2020. Rice products: Nep Thau Dau, Phu Binh district; Phu Luong sticky litchi; Bao Thai rice in Dinh Hoa district... has become a product that generates high income for farmers.

For tea plants: As a specialty and branded product of Thai Nguyen province, the tea growing area has gradually increased over the years. In 2020, the tea-growing area will increase by 5.4% compared to 2016. Besides the increase in quantity, farmers are also interested in improving the quality of tea products. In 2020, the tea area granted VietGAP certificate will reach 2.6 thousand hectares; the production area according to organic standards reaches 127 ha. This helps to improve the reputation and brand of Thai Nguyen tea, and the income of farmers is increasingly improved.

However, for farming livelihood activities, the application of high-tech agriculture, although implemented, has not yet achieved high efficiency. The number of businesses investing in the crop industry is still low.

Livestock farming activities:

Livelihood activities in Thai Nguyen province include the main livestock species: buffaloes, cows, pigs, poultry (chickens, ducks, geese, and geese), goats, sheep, and bees. In, the number of households raising chickens accounts for the

highest proportion (91%) with production increasing from 9,624 thousand heads in 2015 to 14,120 thousand heads in 2020, followed by the percentage of households raising pigs, buffaloes, cows, and goats. and sheep. The number of small-scale breeding households tends to decrease markedly. This is in line with the province's large-scale husbandry orientation and at the same time reduces the possibility of disease in livestock.

Livestock activities play an important role and account for a large proportion of the value of agricultural production. Livestock production shifted towards cooperatives, concentrated on the farm scale, forming a chain of production-consumption linkages. While the output of live-weight buffalo meat, live-weight beef, and live-weight chicken meat tends to increase, the output of pork more than slaughtered tends to decrease (94,961 tons in 2016 to 84,307 tons in 2020). The cause of the decrease in the production of live pigs for slaughter is due to disease in the pig herd during this period.

Source: Thai Nguyen Provincial Statistics Office, 2017, 2021.

Aquaculture livelihood activities:

The number of households engaged in aquaculture in rural areas of Thai Nguyen province accounts for a low proportion and is mainly cultivated on a small scale. The number of households with less than 0.2 hectares of land for aquaculture accounts for the highest proportion (42.3%), while the number of households with 2 hectares of land for

aquaculture or more accounts for only about 5.9% of the households. aquaculture. The area of intensive farming is low (on average, in the period 2011-2020, accounting for about 7% of the area), mainly semi-intensive, extensive, and improved extensive farming. This makes it difficult to support science and technology and apply science and technology to aquaculture and significantly affects the livelihood results of aquaculture households.

Even so, the aquaculture livelihoods of farmers in Thai Nguyen province still achieved a good level of development.

Source: Thai Nguyen Provincial Statistics Office, 2021.

Figure 6 shows us that fishery production tends to increase. The main object of farming is traditional fish, which increases from 5,617 tons in 2010 to 14,504 tons in 2020 and accounts for about 70% of production in the period 2010-2020. Shrimp and other aquatic products account for a low proportion (shrimp: 66 tons in 2010 increasing to 92 tons in 2020). Farmed objects with high economic value account for a low proportion, the farming efficiency is not high, and the livelihood results of aquaculture farmers in Thai Nguyen province are still low, so they have not created interest in investment in production. export.

Forestry livelihood activities:

The number of households with forestry livelihood activities accounts for a low proportion (approximately 0.7%) and mainly owns 5 hectares or more, accounting for about 23%. Forestry livelihood activities of households mainly in Dinh Hoa, Dong Hy, and Phu Luong districts account for about 60%. The output of forest products (wood, firewood, bamboo, bamboo shoots, palm leaves, fresh bamboo shoots, wood ear) tends to increase in the 2016-2020 period. Which, wood production in 2020 increased by 42% compared to 2016, with 80% of new afforestation area planted with high-yield and high-quality Australian Acacia varieties. In Dinh Hoa district, a concentrated cinnamon growing area has been formed with an area of 2.7 thousand hectares. In addition, the successful construction of a model of planting and raising livestock under the forest canopy has opened a new direction in the application of scientific and technical advances to improve the productivity and quality of the forestry industry, helping farmers have better livelihood outcomes.

Non-agricultural livelihood activities:

Non-agricultural livelihood activities of farmer households in Thai Nguyen province are diverse and abundant, which is a significant source of household income. Workers, service businesses, production, and processing of agricultural products... are the main non-agricultural livelihood activities of farmer households in Thai Nguyen province. Currently, Thai Nguyen province has 12 industrial parks that have been making great contributions to not only the province's economy but also to improving livelihood outcomes for farmers. Especially, the Samsung complex with two factories SEVT and SEMV has attracted a large number of farmers working in the factory (3). This is the main non-farm livelihood activity of farm households (accounting for 44%), especially for those whose land has been acquired to serve the land clearance work. Next is service livelihood activities (restaurant business, room rental combined with business) accounting for nearly 20%. The rest are freelance activities, grocery business, mechanical repair, selling iron and household appliances...

2.2.3. Livelihood results of farm households in Thai Nguyen province.

In the period 2012-2020, the average income per capita in both rural and urban areas tends to increase, however, the income disparity between the average income per capita in urban areas and urban areas tends to increase. rural areas are increasing.

The average income per capita in urban areas in 2010 was 1,761,000 VND, 849,000 VND higher than in rural areas (912,000 VND), by 2018, the difference between urban and rural areas increased from 849,000 VND to 2,487,000 VND. In 2020, household income in Thai Nguyen province will be severely affected, especially in urban areas, so the per capita income of urban areas will decrease from 5,706,000 VND to 5,678,000 VND. , while the rural area increased from 3,219,000 VND to 3,541,000 VND. This leads to a narrowing of the per capita income gap between urban and rural areas.

Source: Thai Nguyen Provincial Statistics Office (2021)

Income from agriculture, forestry, and fishery activities accounts for an average of only 17.76% in the period 2012-2020 and tends to decrease (22.7% in 2012 to 14.4% in 2020).). This figure is not only consistent with the current trend of economic restructuring in Thai Nguyen province but also comes from the high-risk investment in agriculture,

forestry, and fishery. However, if the central government and Thai Nguyen provincial government do not have policies to support the agricultural sector and improve income levels for farmers, the risk of national food insecurity is high.

3. Conclusion

Thus, the development of sustainable livelihoods for farmers in Thai Nguyen province is very necessary, especially in the current context, to maintain the food security of the province and the country. This requires not only the efforts of the farmers themselves but also the involvement of the authorities at all levels. Support in terms of policies: land policy, credit policy, vocational training policy, product sales support policy, and education policy will help farmers to solve their problems. develop livelihoods, and improve the material and spiritual life of households.

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